

Original Article

ACTIVITIES OF UNITED NATIONS DEVELOPMENT PROGRAMME IN THE PROVISION OF HEALTH CARE SERVICES FOR HIV/AIDS PATIENTS IN ENUGU STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study investigated the activities of United Nations Development Programmes (UNDP) in provision of health care services for HIV/AIDS patients in Enugu State. One research question and one hypothesis was formulated. Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population for the study was 1,100 HIV/AIDS patients. The sample for the study was 550 HIV/AIDS patients. Simple and proportionate stratified random sampling techniques were used in drawing the sample for the study. The instrument for data collection was a structured 33-items questionnaire titled “United Nations Development Programmes health care services Questionnaire (UNDPHSQ). The instrument was face validated by three research experts and its reliability index was .71. Data collected were analysed using mean and standard deviation for answering research questions while t-test was used in testing the hypothesis. The finding from the study revealed that provisions of Health care facilities by UNDPs was to a great extent. Based on the finding, it was recommended among others that the UNDP should involve the target community in needs identification, planning, execution, monitoring, assessment and evaluation for sustainability of the projects.

Keywords: UNDP, HIV/AIDS, Health Care Services.

Introduction

The United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) is a United Nation agency tasked with helping Countries eliminate poverty and achieve sustainable economic growth and human development. The UNDP emphasizes on developing local capacity towards long-term self-sufficiency and prosperity. Based at the headquarters of the United Nations in New York City, it is the largest UN development aid agency, with offices in 177

countries. The UNDP is funded entirely by voluntary contributions from UN member states.

The UNDP was founded on 22 November 1965 through the merger of the expanded programme of Technical Assistance (EPTA) and the special fund in 1958. The rationale was to “avoid duplicating of their activities”. The EPTA was set up in 1949 to support the economic and Political aspects of

underdeveloped counties, while the special fund was to enlarge the scope of UN technical assistance. The special fund arose from the idea of a Special United Nations Fund for Economic Development (SUNFED) (which was initially known as the United Nations Fund for Economic Development (UNFED)). UNDP is an international non-governmental organization which works in Nigeria and other countries in the world to initiate and support socio-economic projects and programmes for the benefits of the populace. It is a non-profit organization aimed at enhancing development in developing countries through economic empowerment projects. Economic empowerment is state of affairs where the basic needs of the populace are met. This is a society where income levels are high enough to cover basic need, where unemployment is insignificant, where there is easy access to social, medical and educational services, and everyone is treated with dignity and consideration.

In 1980, some 5,211 operational projects were made available to the developing countries, while 52,988 experts in the projects were deployed for advanced study overseas over \$200 million dollars' worth of equipment and specialized contract services. (World Bank, 2015). These services covered five main fields. These fields are:

1. Economic and social planning with particular emphasis on meeting the needs of the least developed countries and the poorest segment of the economic empowerment.
2. Training in a wide range of vocational and professional skills.
3. Stimulating capital investment to help generalize possibilities.
4. Transferring appropriate technologies and stimulating the growth of local technological capacities.
5. Surveying and assessing such development assets as mineral deposits: fuel researches, rivers and sub-surface waters; commercial and export potentials (World Bank, 2011.)

Under UNDP projects, millions of men and women in developing countries including Nigeria, have been equipped with new skills as teacher and industrial instructors, managers, supervisors, entrepreneurs, and product marketers, administrators and civil servants, farming and forestry specialists, factory workers and public utility technicians, engineers, scientists and mechanical personnel (World Bank, 2015). With the widening gap between the rich and the poor in all societies, poverty eradication has become the focus in the United Nations family. Back in Nigeria, UNDP's cardinal mission is to help Nigerians develop their own country. To achieve these objectives, locally initiated activities were being supported through capacity building to eliminate poverty, create jobs for the employed, promote community participation in development and protect the environment.

To promote the process, UNDP with Community Based Organizations (CBO's) and wider civil society institutions and UN agencies, accepted the challenges and is supporting all programmes targeted at reducing and promoting equity. The underlying principle behind the new UNDP approach is the focus on rural women as the ultimate goal of development. Today, the efforts of UNDP and other international organizations have led to the promotion of economic, social, educational, cultural, political and other areas of development where such ties are aimed towards the development of UNDP healthcare, environmental education, community development, moral development and other relevant areas of human endeavour in rural communities. United Nations Development programme is a sine-qua-non for community development in all the focal countries, especially in Nigeria.

Provision of healthcare services is another basic social amenity required to improve the quality of life of citizens. Health is a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity. Health, in humans, is the extent of an individual's continued physical,

emotional, mental and social stability to cope with his or her environment. Dikko (2013) posited that poor people are also disadvantaged by lack of knowledge about prevention of diseases and when to seek health care services. They tend to live in communities that have weak institutions and social norms that are not conducive to good health. The authors further stated that poor people are caught in a vicious circle of poverty which breeds ill health, and which in turn conspired to keep them poor. Provision of health care services is another social basic amenity which is important to the life of citizens in any community..

In terms of communicable diseases, it is revealed that HIV/AIDS, Tuberculosis (TB) and malaria are the world's biggest killers, and all three these diseases have their greatest impact among poor countries and poor people. Tuberculosis is said to kill about 2 million people each year-one person every 15 seconds. It is noted that more than a health issue, TB results from a complex mix of poverty and other social and economic conditions. Poor countries and poor communities are more likely than wealthier ones to be infected with the TB germ and hence develop TB disease. It is instructive to note that low-income countries account for 65 percent of the world's TB cases, and more than 70 percent of TB caused death (Dye, 2014). This is so because the poorer a community is, the greater the likelihood of widespread infection, occasioned by lack of basic health care services poor nutrition, and poorly ventilated housing which contribute to the spread of infection and the development of active TB.

The UNDP is partnering with Enugu state government to enhance healthcare system, focusing on upgrading and modernizing facilities, particularly at the Primary Healthcare level. While the UNDP doesn't directly operate facilities, they are supporting the state government in improving existing ones and establishing new ones like the 260 type – 2 Primary Healthcare Centres (PHCs) across all Political Wards. These PHC'S are being equipped

with digital technology, including tablets, internet connectivity, and an electronic health Record (HER) system, to improve care and data management.

Also UNDP's support extends to the development of the state university of medical and applied sciences (SUMAS), infectious Disease Hospital; the former Colliery Hospital is being upgraded and plays a role in the state's health care system. Lastly UNDP has done great in the provision of Isolation centers like the Nsukka (isolation centre and the parklane hospital Isolation and treatment centre are part of the state's response to infectious diseases

Statement of the Problem

Some United Nations Development programmes operate in the study area, but the host communities skill lack most of the basic health care services especially provision of HIV/AIDS cases. Also they claim that health care services are provided, but obviously most of these infrastructure have broken down while some community based projects which were started had been abandoned. The speedy implementation of these projects would have alleviated the health services of the citizens. The youths in these communities are restive, since they lack visible means of livelihood. Poverty related problems have aggravated, this resulting in low participation of people in community based project such as health care services, high illiteracy rate, high crime rate, unemployment, and vandalism. These problems exist despite the claim of UNDPs that concerted, efforts are being made to improve the standard of living of the people in the study area.

It is against this backdrop that the researcher intends to ascertain the roles or the involvement of UNDP in the provision of health care services for HIV/AIDS patients. Therefore, the problem of this study put in question form, what are the activities of United Nations Development Programmes in the provision of health care services for HIV/AIDS patients in Enugu state, Nigeria? This is the trust of this study.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to ascertain the activities of United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) in provision of Health care services for HIV/AIDs patients in Enugu State.

Research Question

1. To what extent are Health care services provided by UNDP’ for HIV/AID’s Patients in Enugu state?

Hypothesis

H₀: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female citizens on UNDP’s provision of health care services for HIV/AID’s Patients in Enugu State.

Method

The study adopted descriptive research design. The population for the study was 1,100 respondents. Simple and proportionate stratified random sampling techniques were used in drawing the sample for the study. The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire titled: United Nations Development Programmes Health care Services Questionnaire (UNDPHSQ). The instrument was face validated by three experts, two from the department of Continuing Education and Development Studies, while one from the department of Mathematics and Computer Education (Measurement and Evaluation) Unit in Enugu State

University of Science and Technology. Cronbach Alpha method was used to compute the internal consistency of the instrument. A total of 550 copies of the questionnaire were administered to the respondents. 484 copies were properly filled, retrieved and used for the study which showed 94% returned rate.

The instrument has an overall reliability index of .71 which indicate that the instrument was reliable and considered appropriate for data collection. Data collected were analysed using mean and standard deviation was used in answering the research question, while t-test statistic was used in testing the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. In answering the research questions, any item with a mean of 2.50 and above was regarded as very great extent, while those with a mean of less than 2.50 were regarded as very low extent. In testing the hypothesis, when the value of the t-calculated is equal to or more than the critical (table) value, it would not be accepted. On the other hand, when the value of t-calculated is less than the critical (table) value, the hypothesis would be accepted.

Results

To what extent are health care services provision by UNDP for HIV/AID’s Patients in Enugu State?

Table: 1 summary of mean ratings and standard deviation scores of male and female on UNDP’s provision of healthcare services in Enugu State. N=484

S/N	United Nations Development Programme	Male Means	=360 SD	Remark	Female Mean	=124 SD	Remark
1	Provide counseling services on HIV/AIDs cases in community health centres	3.6	0.13	VGE	3.6	0.91	VGE
2	Constructed a modern health centre in some communities	3.7	0.95	VGE	3.6	0.4	VGE
3	Provide health care equipments to community health centres	3.5	0.93	VGE	3.6	0.44	VGE
4	Provide drugs for the treatment of HIV/AIDs patients in communities	3.8	0.11	VGE	3.7	0.35	VGE

5	Free medical treatment in communities	3.5	0.95	VGE	3.7	0.35	VGE
6	Provide transport facilities to health workers to carryout HIV/AIDs campaign in communities	3.7	0.99	VGE	3.6	0.09	VGE
7	Provide funds to enable health workers carryout HIV/AIDs campaign in communities	3.7	0.11	VGE	3.7	0.43	VGE
8	Carryout enlightenment campaigns on how to prevent HIV/AIDs spread in communities	3.5	0.91	VGE	3.5	0.13	VGE
GRAND MEAN		3.61	0.63	VGE	3.62	0.34	VGE

The result in table 1 shows a grand mean of 3.61 and stand deviation of 0.63 indicating that the respondents agreed to a very great extent that

UNDP- Nigeria provides health care services for HIV/AIDS patients in Enugu State.

Hypothesis

There is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female citizens on UNDP provision of Health care services for HIV/AID’s Patients in Enugu State.

Table 2: t-test Analysis for Hypothesis

Group	N	X	SD	Df	t-cal	t-crit	Sig.	Dec.
Male	360	3.61	0.63	472	1.04	2.28	NS	(do not reject hypothesis)
Female	124	3.62	0.34					

From table 2, t-calculated (1.04) is less than t-critical (2.28). Hence, at .05 significant level, the mean ratings of the two groups (male and female) do not differ significantly. Consequently, hypothesis is not rejected as stated, implying that there is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female citizens on UNDP’s provision of Health care services for HIV/AIDs patient in Enugu State.

Discussion

From the findings, the study revealed that both respondents (male and female) rated the UNDP provision of health care services for HIV/AIDs patients to a great extent in Enugu state. Result from the test of hypothesis further stated that the respondents do not differ significantly from their responses on the UNDP’s provision of health care services for HIV/AIDs patients in Enugu State. The findings is in line with World Bank (2016) which

states that poverty is also a cause of ill health. It asserts that poor counties and poor people within countries experience multiple conditions that combine together to cause greater level of ill health than in those who are better off. They asserts that “the poor lack the financial resources to pay or receive adequate training on HIV/AIDs management, patients need is essential. This includes training on sexual history taking and addressing potential provider discomfort. In addition, the provision of health care services for HIV/AIDs patients’ needs in engaging communities with other healthcare services (e.g sexual and reproductive health, material and child health) can improve access and efficiency.

Conclusion

Based on the result of the findings, it was observed that the study concluded that both respondents (male and female) rated the United Nations Development

programmes on the provision of Health care services for HIV/AIDS patients to a very great extent. This included ensuring access to antiretroviral therapy (ART), testing and counseling, and addressing stigma and discrimination furthermore, integrating HIV/AIDS services into primary health care, promoting patient self-management, and providing ongoing support are crucial for improving treatment outcome and quality of life.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion of the study, the following recommendations were made.

1. Integrated service delivery by combining HIV/AIDS services with other healthcare services like antenatal care, TB treatment, and under -5

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services to improve testing, linkage to care, and treatment adherence.

2. Early diagnosis and linkage to care that implement provider initiated HIV/AIDS testing and counseling (PITC) and ensure rapid linkage to Antiretroviral Therapy (ART) for all diagnosed individuals.

3. Comprehensive treatment and management which provides a range of services including medication administration, symptom management, and treatment for opportunistic infections. Ensure access to home based care and palliative support when needed, according to the National Institutes of Health (NIH)

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